

Lack of Familial Gusto in Mahesh Dattani's *Where There's A Will*

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Abstract

Mahesh Dattani is one of the distinguished Indian English playwrights whose penetrating insight into Indian urban society is widely extolled. His play Where There's a Will is based on an upper-middle class industrial Gujarati family and its relation to individuals. Hasmukh Mehta is the protagonist of the play who had overriding influence over his family members until his mistress Kiran overrode his unpleasant and annoying attempts to destroy filial harmony. Hasmukh's dominance over his family members compelled him to believe that he is superior to all and he considered his son as dull as ditch water. He also feared that his son would override him. So he created rifts in the family to exercise his patriarchal dominance over others. After the death of Hasmukh, he ruled over his family through his 'will' that denied property rights to his family members. He made Kiran as his trustee who was a victim of circumstances but she rose to the occasions and created successfully a peaceful space in the 'unhomely home' of Hasmukh. Because of the nature of Hasmukh, there was no happiness, emotional attachment, enjoyment and understanding among the family members.

Keywords: Familial gusto, Will, Patriarchal, Marginalise, Postmodern.

Mahesh Dattani is a renowned playwright in Indian English literature. His play, *Where There's a Will* (1986) explores socio-cultural dynamics of postmodern society. The play is an insight depiction of the underlying tensions, interpersonal relations, and power fabrics existing within an urban middle-class Gujarati family. It is a type of unique critique on the changing ethos and relations in urban India. Moreover, the play exhorts a thoughtful response to gender roles and gender-based power equations existing within present society.

Hasmukh Mehta, the protagonist of the play, wants to control the life of everyone who surrounds him. He not only controls the life of his family members while he was alive but also makes an arrangement to control their lives after his death through his 'will'. Ajit, Hasmukh's son, says his father wants members of the family to dance to his tunes. The 'will' acts as a whip and its agent is Hasmukh's mistress

Kiran Jhaveri. Hasmukh's power of money and greed for absolute control over his family members has fractured the interpersonal relationship within the family. Like a typical modern family, there is a lack of emotional attachment, and understanding for one's views and opinions. Here, the politics of patriarchy not only marginalizes the female but also the male. According to the 'will', Ajit has to attend office nine to five daily and has to learn about business tactics from Kiran for which he will be getting an allowance. Similarly, Preeti will be getting an allowance after she becomes a mother and Sonal will also get an allowance. But they all have to act accordingly to get the benefit. On the surface level, it appears that Kiran too was subordinated by Hasmukh but her vibrant speech to Sonal reveals the truth. Kiran pities Hasmukh and says that he depended on her for everything. She asserts that he was not the decision maker. She also says that Hasmukh did not really want a mistress; he wanted a father. He saw in her a woman who would father him. She also says men never really grow. Sonal was docile with Hasmukh whereas Hasmukh was submissive with Kiran. This shows that Hasmukh held Sonal in the margins and Kiran was beyond it.

The setting of the play *Where There's a Will* is the lavish house of Hasmukh. The word 'lavish' denotes sarcastically that the house is full of properties. In the play, there are not only properties, but the characters also are mere properties. Every traditional Indian business man wants his son to take over the business. Hasmukh is the patriarch and a promising business man. He regards everyone in the house as useless. At first, Hasmukh feels his son Ajit to be bankrupt at the age of twenty three. When Ajit wants five lakhs to modernize the company, the MD father regrets his birth and for a moment even wishes him to be dead. Immediately, he realizes his mistake and modifies his prayer as "God make him a vegetable so that he will not interfere in my way" (8). Hasmukh does not give him liberty to even use the phone at home. When the play begins, Ajit is talking over the phone and Hasmukh enters through the main door. He says, "Ajit, I am expecting a call, you can talk to your friend later" (5). Moreover, the dialogue between Hasmukh and Ajit shows the dominance of Hasmukh over his son:

HASMUKH . Wrong! I Hasmukh Metha, have every right. It's my phone you are using in my house, and it's my business secrets you are leaking to government officers, and my typists your friend is flirting with.

AJIT. Don't I have any rights at all?

HASMUKH. You have the right to listen to my advice and obey my orders. (6)

Hasmukh is a dictator who tells his son, "listen to my advice and obey my orders and polish my shoes every morning" (6). He has a general opinion about women that they are false assurers. Dattani gives a very lively statement to prove the concept. Hasmukh says "if you ask them if breakfast, lunch or dinner is ready, they say yes but it is never so" (4). He calls Preeti, his daughter-in-law as brilliant. According to him, she is after his money, that is the reason why she married Ajit. At a glance one feels that, Hasmukh is a man of steel with correctness at every step. His health chart shows that he is terribly weak. He suffers from high cholesterol and blood pressure as well as an enlarged heart. He says he gets indigestion and ulcer. He blames the family members for his illness: "In the olden days, if you said someone had a large heart, you meant he was generous and loving. Today it means he is receiving high aggravation from his twenty-three-year-old son and his scheming daughter-in-law" (4).

Hasmukh also says that, his son Ajit is a big zero and if at all Ajit makes sense, it is because the big zero has a one in front. The number one is unmistakable Hasmukh himself. In this manner another earning member of the family is criticized. For both Ajit and Hasmukh, their family relationship is secondary when compared to money. This is the reason for Ajit to expect his father's property

after his death and for the same reason, the 'will' is a great disappointment. Ajit says on the phone, "Actually I don't give a damn. I mean one day it's all going to be mine. And then I can do all the things I've wanted to do. All the changes, I've been thinking of making" (4-5). But the 'will' of his father disappoints him a lot.

Hasmukh Mehta has no respect and love for his wife Sonal. She is to him good for nothing. In fact, she is a chaste and obedient wife, but what Hasmukh expects from his wife is something disgusting one. He says; "Then I should be very happy man. I've got a loving wife who has been faithful to me like any dog would be" (23). His words throw ample light on the fact that Hasmukh's notion of faithful wife is as good as faithful dog that acts as per provided training without using her own discretion. Actually, Sonal is an innocent and ignorant woman who doesn't know about his sexual lust and his enjoyment with night women. She is a devoted and decent wife, but her husband is perverted and a rude creature. At the end, Sonal and Kiran join hands to eradicate the evil of sexual colonialism. They are gifted with the ability to assess and subsequently shaking off unjust shackle of patriarchy.

Sonal does not have any of the above mentioned aspects of married woman. Hasmukh is highly dissatisfied with the manner in which his life has been spent with no one living up to his expectation, the way he had lived up to his father's expectation. Hasmukh's aim is to seek revenge through his 'will', which will be released only after his death. He suffers from blood pressure, cholesterol, diabetes and salt in the urine. He was prone to so many life risks due to his disorders, but he blames his family members for his physical sufferings. He does not expect death which confronts him very soon.

As a matter of fact, all troubles come out of Hasmukh's false notions of joy and happiness of life. He considers domination as the only and final system which can bring joy and happiness in the family. Ironically he fails to understand that domination kills the joy of human heart and soul. Domination flourishes killing other's self and identity. It is, in fact, biggest hurdle in building up the premise of happiness.

After sometime Hasmukh is dead and he lazes around as a ghost. From this onwards, instead of Hasmukh, his ghost speaks. He sees his ad in obituary as 'Garment Tycoon Dead'. As Hasmukh mentions all are in anguish, but at the same time, they are all waiting for the next thing to happen. Exactly after one week, the concerned officers come to read out the 'will'. The family members are drenched in a shock. Through the following conversation among the family members, Dattani has shown the agony and distrust of their mind:

SONAL. He has ruined us! Minal will be shocked when she hears this.

PREETI. To hell with Minal! As if it makes any difference to her!

SONAL. If I wasn't so exhausted, I would stop you from talking about my sister like that!

AJIT (groaning also). He has ruined us! The old man has taken us for a nice ride. (28)

Preeti accuses Sonal that if she had been nicer, it would not happen like this. She says he wasn't nice to her but she adjusted. Sonal leaves an open statement that she would have left him if she knew he had a mistress. They very soon find out that they were not liable to make use of the property immediately. Preeti wants to contest the 'will'. Sonal says he must be mad to do this to them. Preeti says, they could get the certificate to prove that he was a senile. She goes still further and says that they could prove through Doctor Jhunjhunwalla that he was ill for the past few months. Very soon, Kiran enters the house and gets herself self introduced.

Then Ajit recaps the 'will'. It dissolved when he is forty five years old, the year when his father feels him to have attained complete maturity, he can do what he wants with that money. Ajit tells

Minal that his mother was not at fault. Usually, it is the lady who is blamed for men's fault. This is patriarchy, this is domination and thus it means suppression. He says that his father has formed a Charitable Trust. He has donated all his property, finance and shares to the Trust including the house they live in. They would all get an allowance from that Trust monthly. Sonal reminds the family members that Ajit has to attend office every day at 9am and he can only leave at 6pm. He even has to have his lunch there. The 'will' also stated that no new business project would be sanctioned for Ajit, and Sonal continues to say that, if they do not abide by the 'will', Kiran tries to make them understand that she had no hand in this issue. Sonal becomes weary and Preeti stresses the point of suppression of the whole family. The whole family stood subordinated to the lady Kiran as per the 'will' and it was publicly noticed by everyone.

Kiran declares that there is no proof for their relationship. Preeti pronounces that they must contest the 'will'. She makes it very clear that she is only the trustee and not the owner. It is her job and she gets a salary for it. Kiran says that everything rightfully belongs to three of them provided they follow office as usual. Mrs Mehta shall get a regular allowance to run the house and little more for her personal expenses. Preeti too will get an allowance, when she becomes a mother. When her child is twenty-one, the Trust automatically dissolves. Its holdings will be transferred to Ajit and his heirs. She also tells them that her main duty is to run the Mehta group of companies on behalf of Ajit, and she has the authority to make all the major decisions in the interest of the companies. Her duty also extends to train Ajit and delegate responsibilities to him in phases. Most importantly of all instructions, she must leave her husband and stay here as part of Mehta family. Sonal feels terribly irritated. She feels that Hasmukh had planned the presence of Kiran, just to remind her of her inadequacy. She feels that it was his master plan.

At last, they have no choice but to allow Kiran to stay back at home. They decide to make her stay outside the house. But Sonal decides to make her stay in her own room. She says, "She can share my room! Mrs Jhaveri and I have a lot to discuss" (43). In her short stay, Kiran finds out the crime committed by Preeti. She had interchanged the tablets for BP and vitamin, which Hasmukh used for his health. Kiran enquires about the issue to Preeti and Preeti immediately agrees. As Hasmukh himself mentions, Preeti married Ajit only for his money.

Hasmukh Mehta's parental authority was a tension not only for Sonal and Preeti, but also for Kiran. She confesses that she managed her relationship with an old and erratic man like Hasmukh, only for money. Here Dattani explores the Post-colonial and multi-cultural India. It has been adroitly clear that due to his lack of ethics and sexual transgression, Hasmukh Mehta was flung out of the frying pan into the fire. Hasmukh died many times, his corporeal demise was seen when he was enjoying cigar that the best treatment was given by the playwright to an egoist having self-pride. While Kiran made a full stop to all types of friction in the Mehta family, his ghost could not stand with a re-energized home free from his hellish dominance.

Mahesh Dattani's entire work may be seen as a depiction of conflict between the older and the younger generations. He has accorded greater importance to those issues which largely remain hidden in our society. He has the unique capacity to read the rumblings of contemporary Indian society and smell the unceasing clash between tradition and modernity. Family relations are the keys to the plots of Dattani's plays. He basically deals with issues which are considered to be invisible taboo by the Indian society like gender discrimination, homosexuality, transgender, patriarchy, communalism and so on. He takes his subjects from within the complicated dynamics of modern urban families. Families are composed of unique individuals. That uniqueness stems from the fact that every individual has creativity and free will and he/she is able to make his/her own choices.

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